

Exploring Voluntary and Involuntary Migration: Modern Migration Trends in Perspective

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The study explores modern migration trends to establish whether they are voluntary or involuntary. The study is relevant because of migrants' classification into economic and refugees, and the 1951 U.N. Convention's refugees protection against economic migrants. Modern refugees demography (women & children hold no political opinions) are different from the 1950s Soviet dissident refugees, mostly intellectuals from cities who held different political opinions and were generally persecuted. Grounded in Massey et al's migration theories classification as "originators" and "propositions", the study explores voluntary and involuntary modern migration trends. A focus on these two areas is what sets this study apart from similar researches. After conducting a meta-study of the relevant qualitative information on these areas, findings reveal that migrants' classification as economic and refugees needs to be revisited. Because it does not portray modern migration trends, which comprises voluntary and involuntary elements. Migration drivers, such as push (war & drought), are coerced, and pull (amenities), which compels migrants to migrate have an element of forced migration. These factors are blended sometimes to trigger modern migration. The paper argues that modern migration, unlike in olden days, where voluntary migrants (economic) and involuntary migrants (refugees) were easy to identify, modern migration consists of both voluntary and involuntary migration. Some of these are triggered by combined factors, namely, industry concentration in cities, practices (gayism), and drought, which affects people's livelihoods. The paper therefore calls for re-visitation of migrants classification, and the U.N. 1951 Convention's re-examination to be abreast with modern migration.

Keywords: Migration drivers, forced migration, coerced, refugees, economic migrants

The study explores modern migration trends to establish whether they are voluntary or involuntary. The study is relevant because of migrants' classification into economic, non-economic, refugees and asylum seekers, and the 1951 United Nations (U.N.) Convention's refugees protection against economic migrants. Meanwhile, the modern refugee demography (women, children & ordinary men hold no political opinions different from the authorities) is different from the 1950s refugees, who were Soviet dissidents, decent men, mostly intellectuals from cities who held different political opinions and were generally persecuted (Dlamini et al., 2020). Moreover, the availability of arms, porous borders, and the strong solidarity of the nations, especially in the European region, to receive Ukrainian refugees, informs this study. In contrast, Syrian and Afghan refugees and migrants were 'neglected' and discriminated against (Borges, 2024). Grounded in Massey et al.'s (1993) research migration theories classification as "originators" and "propositions", the study aims to explore voluntary and involuntary modern migration trends.

Migration is defined as an individual or people's movement from one place to another (Bell & Osti, 2010). Migration is an aspect of

human nature. Migrants migrate from their environment to another distance where they decide to live (Vorvornator, 2024a). This could be permanent or semi-permanent. Migration can be undertaken across the borders of a country known as international migration (Foged & Peri, 2016). But the most common form of migration is movement within the country, referred to as internal migration (Olaitan & Okoye, 2025). Different types of migration are identified in human history. Migration is categorised as emigration (out-going) and immigration (in-coming) (Vorvornator, 2024b). Similarly, migration is considered as voluntary and involuntary depending on the circumstances individuals migrate. Voluntary migrants are migrants who migrate of their own will. This involves economic migrants seeking better living standards in country of destination (CODs) (Docquier et al., 2014).

Voluntary migration can be identified as international retirement; this means the retirement becomes the push factor, while the pull factor is the pleasant climatic environment. Irregular migration and seasonal migration are examples of voluntary migration (De Haas et al., 2019). Labour migration could overlap between the voluntary and involuntary migration. Skilled labour is demanded by the CODs, whereas unskilled labour is usually in numbers, and this is where irregular migrant anchor (Davis, 2021). Involuntary migrants migrate because of circumstances beyond their control (Bell et al., 2010). For instance, migrants migrate due to war and violent situations to save their lives (refugees & asylum seekers). These are the migrants protected by the UN (1951) Convention. At a point, both voluntary and involuntary migration are difficult to differentiate. The concern of this study is to establish whether modern migration trends are voluntary and involuntary.

Generally, migration has social, demographic and economic effects in both COOs and CODs (Korsi, 2021). Migration occurs in the combination of factors, which Lee (1966) classified as push and

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pull factors. Push factors are the discomfoting conditions such as insecurity, insufficient job opportunities, desertification, flooding, death threats, poverty and war. On the other hand, pull factors are political stability, better services, attractive climates and fewer natural disasters (Olaitan & Okoye, 2025; Lee, 1966). These factors may be voluntary and involuntary and in some instances they overlap. For instance, a Ugandan who lives in poverish environment and at the same time, she is a lesbian, and the society abhor such practices before her migration; where will she be classified? Is it voluntary or involuntary migration? The overlap in modern migration trends, which consists of a mix-bag migration is concerned of this study aims to establish. The paper aims to contribute that unlike in the olden days where migration is classified as voluntary (economic), and involuntary (refugees), the modern migration comprises both voluntary and involuntary (mixed-bag migration). Therefore, over seventy-five years now, there is a need to re-examine the 1951 U.N. Convention to cater to all migrants since modern migration is a mixed bag or comprises both voluntary and involuntary migration.

The study includes a theoretical framework classification by Massey et al. (1993) establish the existing migration theories, which are classified under originators and propositions. We then include a literature review which establishes argument about the modern migration trends, whether they are voluntary or involuntary. The study's methodology is based on a literature review, which can otherwise be called a meta-study, and we explain how this was done under that subheading. The paper ends with findings, conclusion, and recommendations. The next section presents theoretical framework of the study.

Theoretical Framework

Theoretical Clarification of Modern Migration Trends

Migration is dynamic, regards the question of whether migration is voluntary or involuntary will continue to be an interesting topic in the years to come. Massey et al. (1993) in an attempt to simplify migration theories, grouped them into two namely: originator and proposition. The scholars identified the originator theories as neo-classical, New Economic Labour Migration (NELM), dual labour economy and world market system, whereas the proposition theories identified are social networking, cumulative causation, and institutional theories.

The Originator Theories

The originator theories such as Neo-classical theory posits that wage differences as per the capitalist practices force migrants from the periphery to the core (Massey, 2015). This means differences in salaries between COOs and CODs lead to migration. Bojas (1990) concurred that the disparity in wages attracted and pulled the labour force from rural to urban areas. The decision to migrate is taken by individuals without family members (Massey et al., 1993). This implies that modern economic and social changes exacerbate structural concentrations in the core regions, which pull labourers involuntarily from periphery to urban. Migrants involuntarily migrate to cities due to unemployment conditions in periphery. The paper argues that modern migrants migrate involuntarily not voluntarily, due to the uneven distribution of resources unlike in the olden days. Regarding the UN Geneva Convention (1951) non-refoulement principle should be extended to protect all migrants

instead of the refugees and asylum seekers only. Besides, migration is considered to be voluntary but migrants were compelled by the wage disparity to migrate, which makes migration involuntary instead of voluntary.

Massey (1990) elaborates that NELM theory occurs in unfavourable conditions in COOs, which trigger migration. Households decide to send a prominent family member abroad to earn income as an 'insurance' during financial crises (Massey, 1990). These decisions are taken due to a lack of non-farm income for the households. The decision to migrate is taken together with close relatives and friends. The family member believed to be energetic, versatile, endowed with a higher qualification, and skilful is selected to migrate. Household insurance is derived through the means of remittances, which can be described as brain gains. The brain gains are the rewards or remuneration migrants send to the non-migrants or their families. Migrants believe migration serves as an 'insurance' against any risk or uncertainties. The NELM theory asserts that people consider migration as a means of diversification to avert adverse situations that drive them involuntarily from their COOs (Stark & Levhari, 1982). Why are economic migrants considered voluntary migrants under modern migration trends? Vollrath's (2009) research on the dual economy created a bifurcated economy that attracts both skilled and unskilled labour. The bifurcated economy comprises the primary and secondary sector activities. The primary sector absorbs the skilled labourers, whereas the secondary sector employs the unskilled labourers. The bifurcation economy forces workers from COOs to CODs in search of greener pastures.

Wallerstein (1974) posits that the World market system originates as a result of colonisation, capitalist practices, and modernisation, which leads to the concentration of economic activities in the developed and core regions at the expense of the periphery. Migrants are forced (involuntary) from the periphery to the core to improve their living standards (Wallerstein, 1974). Because life in the rural settlements is characterised by high unemployment and poverty. Zelinsky (1971) hypothesis of mobility transition also explored that the modernisation process, which leads to economic and social changes, contributed to force migration from rural-to-urban. These theories, as it stands considered migration patterns in terms of the industrialisation nation to be involuntary rather than voluntary. Simpson's (2017) and Lee's (1966) push and pull theory elaborates on factors that compel migrants from COOs and CODs, and factors that trigger migration. Lee's (1966) push and pull theory explains two countries apart that is the South and North countries. The origin countries known as developing are troubled with problems such as unemployment, unfavourable climatic conditions, and lower productivity in the economy, which results in high inflation (Li & Schleicher, 2010).

The CODs are purported to have better living standards, existing job opportunities, and media freedom. The CODs are regarded by migrants as if the pavements were constructed with gold (Crush & Ramachandran, 2010). Migrants in this regard are considered to be rational beings (*homo economicus*). Migrants only migrate, if they realise the conditions in CODs are better off than in the COOs (Muniz et al., 2010). In other words, costs and benefits analysis is considered before migration. This implies that if the benefits weigh more than costs, the decision to migrate is implemented, whereas when the costs are more than benefits, migration decision is dropped (Muniz et al., 2010). However, others migrate without considering the conditions in COOs; they just migrate to save their lives or run

away from volatile and violence situations; these are the people that can be classified as refugees. This implies refugees are forced by the circumstances beyond their control in COOs such as war and violent conditions; just as like economic migrants who leave their origin due to unbearable conditions.

Other migrants may decide not to migrate from their COOs but circumstances such as family, drought, pestilence and others might force them to migrate; they are referred to as economic migrants (Simpsons, 2017). In other developments, unemployment may trigger migration as a push factor, but a migrant experiences racism, which is abscorned by the local culture before s/he migrates to save his or her life; will it be classified as voluntary or involuntary migration? The argument is that both refugees and economic migrants involuntarily migrate based on circumstances beyond their control. Is modern migration voluntary or involuntary?

The Proposition Theories

The propositions expressed by Massey (1990) indicate that factors that trigger migration change as migration continues to progress. After the earlier migrants in the community were forced to migrate involuntarily by environmental factors such as drought, bushfires, floods, and famine, beyond their control, migration became common through the assistance of the pioneer migrants, in terms of providing information to the non-migrants. This reduces the costs and risks associated with migration. Social capital and relations that exist between the migrants and non-migrants in the community serve as a tool for integrating processes and resources for the community members (Massey et al., 1990).

Massey's (2015) research further established that due to social capital in the communities, institutions spring up to provide services for the members. These organisations assist in migration processes such as pre-migration (securing documents & visas), migration (actual day to travel), and post-migration (arrival in the host nations in terms of securing accomodations). Institutions range from recruiting agencies, people smugglers, and humanitarian organisations such as Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), and lawyers. Through, institutions establishment, new channels of migrant-receiving communities are created in the CODs (Goss & Lindquist, 1995). Helps are extended to the new migrants in terms of job seeking, accommodation and providing guidance about the dos and don'ts in the CODs. Migrants' network perpetuates and becomes causative in the community. From the aforementioned discussion, are modern migration trends voluntary or involuntary? Do modern economic migrants and refugees' demographics differ from those of the olden days economic migrants and refugees? The next section presents the literature review of the study.

Review of Literature

Arguments for and the discourse of voluntary and involuntary in modern migration trends.

Modern Migration and a Globalized World

Globalisation is defined as the growing interdependence of cultures, economy and population brought about by cross-borders exacerbate migration rather than retarding it. Globalisation enhances migration from one area to another (Johnston, 1981). Migration is concerned with culture, livelihoods, devastating situations and exile (Massey, 2015). It is determined by a set of factors, namely: economic, social, environmental, demographic and political, and to a large extent the

behaviour, aspiration, and perception of individuals (Enaifoghe & Maduku, 2019). These factors, according to the existing literature, compel migrants to migrate voluntarily or involuntarily. As a result, migration theories are 'disjointed' and cut across disciplines such as Development Studies, Sociology, Geography, Economics, and History (Massey, 2015).

Intense analysis of the current trends of economic migrants and refugees; do economic and political factors make migrants migrate voluntary and involuntary? Currently, climatic conditions such as drought, bush-fires, and floods trigger people to migrate involuntary unlike in the olden days, when people migrate voluntary. Likewise, the current refugees demography are different from the olden days refugees who were Soviet dissent intellectuals and held different political opinions from the ruling government. The modern dynamics of migration drivers make it difficult to establish whether migrants are economic migrants or refugees (Aiyar et al., 2016). This implies classifying migrants into voluntary and involuntary cannot hold water in modern migration trends.

Theoretical Literature Consideration

Colonisation, modernisation and contemporary capitalism unlike socialism lead to the concentration, and centralisation of industries in the core rather than periphery in cities or countries (Massey, 2015). Economic activities are located in advanced countries at the expense of developing countries. In developing countries, the case is not different where economic activities are concentrated in the cities compared to the rural areas (Vorvornator, 2024c). This leads to displacement and marginalisation of periphery dwellers, and they are excluded from mainstream economic participation (Dalgado Wise, 2011).

The consequences lead to uneven development between the core and periphery in terms of geographical spaces, social classes, and unequal income distribution and wealth, creates the gap between the poor and the rich; being it in developed and developing, cities and rural areas (Massey, 2015). The uneven development between cities, rural settlements and developed and developing countries lead to structural conditions that result in a massive migration of marginalised, dispossessed and excluded population (IOM, 2018).

It is therefore clear that current migration decisions taken by the families or individuals as stipulated by the neo-classical and NELM theory are due to elements of force circumstances (Porumbescu, 2015; Massey, 2015). For instance, the neo-classical theory stipulates that migrants migrate because of differences in wages to the developed nations (Porumbescu, 2015) whereas the NELM theory indicates that due to unfavourable conditions in COOs migrants were compelled to migrate to avoid the harsh conditions (Massey, 2015).

Zelinsky's (1971) research on the hypothesis of mobility transition explains that the modernisation process results in structural, social changes, and economic restructuring in the developed and developing nations, which also contributed to forced migration from rural to urban areas. Zelinsky (1971) maintains that industrialisation in the developed nations spark forced migration rather than hindering it from the periphery to the core. These theories, as they stand considered migration patterns in terms of the industrialisation nation to be involuntary rather than voluntary.

As discussed above from the neo-classical theory (wage differences), NELM (harsh economic conditions), transitory mobility (structural changes) in favour of the advanced nations make

migration involuntary from periphery to the core (Massey, 2015; Porumbescu, 2015; Zelinsky, 1971). The paper argues that concentration of resources in the core makes migrants migrate to better their lives; they did not undertake the migration voluntarily but rather involuntarily. Further, the current migration drivers assume mixed-bag migration rather than pull and push factors (Simpson, 2017). This implies a migrant migrates due to economic reasons, face with war situations in place of settlement and later undertakes secondary migration to another area to save his life. Is the individual an economic migrant (voluntary) or refugees (involuntary)?

Migration as Compulsive Displacement

Modern migration consists of both internal and international is caused by the contradictory and disorderly dynamic of uneven development as a result of the capitalist system (Delgado Wise, 2011). In other words, migration currently cannot be disputed to be the 'brand' of 'compulsive displacement', a new pattern of 'forced migration' (Delgado Wise, 2011). According to Delgado Wise (2011), modern migration portrays the following characteristics: "Firstly, migration is a large expulsion process resulting from a downward spiral of social regression triggered by the deprivation of production means and subsistence, pillaging, violence, and catastrophe that jeopardise the survival of large segments of the population in places of origin. The above is not a simple cumulative or gradual process, but an actual breakdown of social order brought about by structural adjustment policies (SAP), domination and wealth concentration strategies, which have to attain extreme levels and are forcing a massive contingent of the population through accumulation by dispossession mechanisms". This implies being uncomfortable with situations in COO forces people to migrate nationally and internationally to guarantee their families' subsistence.

Márquez and Delgado Wise (2011) continued that "Secondly, compulsive displacement imposes a restriction on the mobility of the migrant workforce, depreciating and subjecting them to conditions of high vulnerability, precariousness, and extreme exploitation. If the process of expulsion is the reprisal of the original accumulation modes characteristics of the first historical stages of capitalism, the current liberalisation of the workforce is fated to face obstacles in the labour market internationally. Migrant-receiving states regulate immigrant entry with punitive and coercive instruments that devalue labour, in addition to violating human rights and criminalising migrants. Conditions for labour exploitation, social exclusion, as well as risks experienced at different stages of transit and settling, jeopardise the lives of migrants".

This study's concern is not to establish that migration is no longer voluntary or involuntary but rather to explore that modern migration comprises both voluntary and involuntary elements. Regard classification of migrants into economic and refugees, where others are protected (UN 1951 Convention; Johnston, 1981) and some migrants are discriminated against does not hold water in modern migration trends.

Voluntary or Involuntary as Modern-day Migration Drivers

The authors interrogate the notion of whether migration drivers in modern days are voluntary or involuntary. As explained above migration drivers have assumed new roles as a result of a division of labour, specialisation and concentration of industries instead of

decentralisation in the core at the expense of the periphery (Flahaux & De Haas, 2016; Márquez & Delgado Wise, 2011). It is further explained that geographical spaces and social classes result in uneven development and generate new types of migration, which can be called 'forced migration' (Crock & Parsons, 2023).

Notwithstanding, forced migration does not relate to all migrants but there is an element of voluntary when it comes to migration (Castles, 2003). It must be noted that migration drivers do not act alone, but interact and bond together with each other, and forced placement on individuals, as well as families (Boochani, 2018). For instance, occurrences of drought (environment) lead to food insecurity (economic) situations, definitely affect personal characteristics such as household wealth and personal resources (social), and may force individuals or families to migrate.

Moreover, civil unrest (political) could threaten food security (economic) and deplete the resources (social) of the people. In the field of human rights, only asylum seekers, refugees, and displaced migrants are known as forced migrants. The paper argues modern migration is involuntary, unlike in the olden days; therefore, migrants' acclamation on only refugees and asylum seekers is inappropriate, but rather all migrants were forced to migrate, so the non-refoulement principle should be extended to them (UN Geneva Convention, 1951). According to the International Organisation of Migration (IOM) refugee is;

"Anyone who, owing to the well-founded fear of precautions for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinions is outside the country of his or her nationality and unable or owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself or herself of the protection of that country" (Geneva Convention, 1951, Act 1A).

An asylum seeker is considered as "any person who seeks safety from persecution or serious harm in a country other than his or her own and awaits a decision on the application for refugee status under relevant international and national instructions. In case of a negative decision, the person may leave the country and may be expelled, unless permission to stay is provided on humanitarian grounds" (IOM, 2018).

The quotes indicate that migrants, more especially, economic and non-economic, refugees and asylum seekers differ, but in modern migration trends, drivers of migration are similar if not the same. In that vein, the paper aims to explore the new faces of human mobility, whether they are voluntary or involuntary. The study is timely and important because of the global rise in migration, especially in developing countries to the only ten immigrant countries notably the United States, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand (Global Migration Data Analysis Centre, 2016) which makes migration a 'thorny' issue.

Migration as a Result of Unemployment, Dispossession and Exclusion

Migration statistics indicate that most current labour migration falls under the category, which comprises xenophobia, racism, discrimination, exploitation, criminalisation, and extreme vulnerability (Global Migration Data Analysis Centre, 2016). It is the largest form of forced migration across the globe, estimated to be over 200 million international 'economic' migrants (International Labour Organisation (ILO), 2019). This implies migrants migrate not on their own accord but due to force and coercion behind their migration.

Instead of identifying and analysing the risks, dangers and problems associated with migration drivers, the term 'economic' migrants is employed (Forray et al., 2024). In other words, the use of economic migrants indicates that migration is undertaken without any compelling circumstances and coercive factors such as marginalisation, vulnerability, insecurity, and persecution which migrants are subjected to in their COOs (Delgado Wise, 2011; Wise & Covarrubias, 2009). The economic migrants migrate through the means of involuntary means rather than voluntary means, as the existing literature indicates.

Migration due to Civil Unrest, Violence, Tribal Conflicts, and Catastrophe

Drivers of migration such as environmental (drought & natural disasters), economic (food security & unemployment), political (persecution & discrimination), social (sexism & family problems), major infrastructural development, and urbanisation may seriously affect individuals, families, communities, societies and social groups and force them to abandon their places of origin and in some cases their country to a new destination (Parkins, 2010; Simpson, 2017). These categories of migration drivers affect all migrants, irrespective of being economic migrants, non-economic migrants, refugees and asylum seekers (Enh et al., 2024; Simpson, 2017).

However, migrants such as refugees and asylum seekers are only regarded as forced migrants and protected by the non-refoulement principle established in the U.N. Geneva Convention 1951. This is considered an unfair classification of migrants according to the literature in migration studies (Bauer & Zimmermann, 1999). The above phenomena usually occur in the global South and trigger migration to the global North, or from developing to developed countries. According to UNHCR (2019), as of 2019 statistics for refugees, asylum seekers and internally displaced migrants totalled over 79.4 million. The refugees formed close to 20.2 million, asylum seekers over 3.7 million and internally displaced migrants were 43.9 million (UNHCR, 2019).

The paper, therefore, maintains that economic and non-economic migrants were also coerced and forced by various conditions in their original places before they migrated. If the compelling drivers before migration did not exist in the COOs, migrants might not migrate internally or from the global South to the North. In other words, if development were not to be centralised in the core at the expense of periphery countries due to capitalism, migrants would have remained in their place of origin. Therefore, migration drivers cannot be classified as voluntary and involuntary in modern migration trends.

Deportation of Immigrants and Repatriation

Deportability (threats of deportation) and repatriation are the growing trends in the destination countries of returning undocumented migrants without their own will as migration diplomacy (Tsourapas, 2017). Of course, the migrants are not charged with criminal acts; the situation is coined in the field of migration as 'double forced migration' (Delgado Wise, 2011). Migrants leave their COOs due to coercive and unbearable conditions; they are forced to return to meet the persecution, atrocity, vulnerability, and insecurity they were running away from (UNHCR, 2019).

In the case of refugees and asylum seekers, the Geneva

Convention, 1951, Act 1A was established in the non-refoulement principle that en masse deportation or repatriation of refugees is prohibited, unless individuals pose security threats to the host nation (UN Geneva Convention, 1951). However, the non-refoulement clause does not protect other types of migrants. This is the basis of this paper to educate the international authorities that migration drivers are no longer voluntary or involuntary but rather comprises both elements. Therefore, there is a need to re-examine the non-refoulement principle to meet the modern migration trends.

Human Trafficking and Smuggling

Human trafficking and smuggling are forms of forced migration that occur because of barrier control, restriction and restrictive measures implemented by destination countries (Global Migration Data Analysis Centre, 2016). As a consequence, human trafficking and smuggling have increased over the years to become lucrative businesses for individuals and undocumented businesses (Global Migration Data Analysis Centre, 2016). Human trafficking is a synonym for coercion, abduction, and forced migration and its activities involve serious violations of human rights, leading to sexual exploitation and illicit adoptions.

To curb the human trafficking rates in society, the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organised Crime was signed in Palermo in the year 2000 (UN, 2000). Transnational Organised Crime protocol aims to sanction and punish the perpetrators of heinous crimes against humanity, more especially against women and children. The estimation of IOM (2019) posits that over 40 million forced migrants are due to human trafficking all over the world, both internally and internationally.

Lack of Job Opportunities and Qualifications for Migrants

Capitalism, structural imbalances, and restructuring of an innovative system, which results in centralisation instead of decentralisation, in the core rather than the periphery, contributed to these types of forced migration in third-world countries (OECD, 2022). In the global South, qualified professionals find it difficult, if not impossible to get jobs to match their suitable qualifications in their country (Clemens & Hunt, 2017). This situation forced over 30 million professionals to migrate from the South to the North to fulfil their labour and intellectual capacity development (OECD, 2022). Because there is a high level of demand for skilled migrants compared to supply in European countries, the United States and Canada.

Moreover, there is the possibility to acquire further skills and training which are associated with innovation in the field of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) (OECD, 2022). In that vein, skilled workers' migrants termed as economic migrants should be revisited and re-examined because they (migrants) were forced by unemployment conditions to migrate, the paper maintains that they are forced migrants. The authors are aware that other forms of voluntary migration may take a short period in the form of leisure and recreation, businesses, and seeking medical attention. However, with equal development in both core and periphery, all things being equal, some of these migrations could have been avoided. Because all those facilities and activities could have been found in the COOs. In the case of North-South migration, it is because of establishment of multinational companies that compel people to migrate. For instance, the establishment of the Coca-Cola Companies by Western

nations in developing countries. If these companies had been established in the developing nations prior to the North-South migration could have been seized (Aldén et al., 2015).

Therefore, capitalist characteristics of underdevelopment result in this involuntary migration, which could be regarded as forced migration. With equal and balanced development, migrants could seek leisure and recreation, medical attention and business activities in their COOs without migration. The inadequate medical facilities, and recreational facilities in the less developed countries coerced migrants to migrate to the advanced countries. The modern migration trends, which comprises both voluntary and involuntary elements should be examined to address the lapses in the UN 1951 Convention to be abreast with time. The next section presents research methodology of the study.

Method

This study began with a literature review (LR) exploring voluntary and involuntary migration under moder migration perspective. Taherdoost (2021, p. 11) states that LR is "the process of accessing published secondary data". The definition explains two distinct characteristics. Firstly, it implies that LR adopts only data from secondary sources, not primary sources. Information from secondary sources was used in this exploration, and these sources included articles, journals, and organizational and non-organizational reports (Maxwell, 2021). The second implication of Taherdoost's assertion is that LR is desktop research and is not conducted in the field (Taherdoost, 2021). Another way to define such a study is a 'meta study', because it reviews and organises the information presented in existing studies in a coherent way.

Key search engines such as Research Gate, JSTOR, Google Scholar, Web of Science and EBSCOhost were consulted for this study. Migration websites and journals including International Migration organization and United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNCHR) were consulted. Search terms such as: 'voluntary', 'involuntary', and 'migration', 'modern migration', were employed.

The study acquired 1453 ideal publications; 1444 of these were derived from an electronic search, and nine were found through forward and back searches. Eligibility assessment was conducted and a total of 50 articles were selected, through the following eligibility criteria: a) publications concentrate on either or both on voluntary and involuntary and modern migration trends; b) publications focus on voluntary and involuntary migration; c) publications date in 2015 or later; d) publication in English (Creswell, 2021). Eleven years articles were selected to limit the scope of this study because it explores the phenomena related to unprecedented events in migration history. World conflicts since that time have resulted in rising numbers of refugees, including those from Afghanistan and Syria, the Arab Spring migration to Europe, and current Ukrainian refugees.

Templier and Paré (2015) identify six steps in examining LR namely: a) identifying primary research objectives and questions; b) exploring the important articles; c) making inclusions; d) exploring the articles' quality and their content; e) extracting data, and f) analysing data. All articles considered unnecessary were excluded. After an eligibility check, we proceeded to the data extraction and analysis stage. Data extraction deals with coding significant articles related to this study. We adopted 'framework analysis', which deals with methodological processes and procedures. We then analysed

and extracted the relevant literature.

The guiding process which facilitate both analysing relevant data is described by Armstrong (2021) as "sifting, charting and sorting materials according to key themes and issues". Simply, familiarization is undertaken to have actual knowledge about articles' importance. Thereafter, we identified the thematic framework centring on theories and ideas that emerged from reading on voluntary and involuntary migration. Indexing undertaken through sifting the data related to particular themes; charting the information processed to sort out important headings and sub-headings during thematic framework stage (Creswell, 2021). These were the processes that we followed. Mapping and interpretation-which entails assembling and analysing all criteria features of dataset-and a synthesis of information were performed.

Key articles selected for the study used a range of qualitative and quantitative methodologies. Meta-analysis for the quantitative data was ignored because this research method was different. This implies that this research did not share common methods or the same variables with a quantitative research methodology. Textual information was mapped and presented accordingly by employing a framework-analysis approach. The theories and LR used here present a broad picture, one that forms baseline information data and enhances comprehension of the past literature on voluntary and involuntary migration (Maxwell, 2021).

The LR on voluntary and involuntary migration has helped to avoid the duplication of existing works by other researchers. However, there are setbacks to this method. For example, since not all academic search engines were employed, there could be some past literature that was left out. The next section presents the findings of this study.

Results and Discussion

Is Modern Migration Trends Voluntary or Involuntary?

The study's findings reveal that modern migration trends consists of both voluntary and involuntary elements of migration which are triggered by push and pull factors (Simpson, 2017). Under these factors are economic, environmental, political, and social conditions that affect individuals, groups of people, family and communities to migrate (economic, non-economic, voluntary & forced migrants) (Simpson, 2017). The factors that trigger migrants from the periphery to the core nations are found to force migrants to migrate without their will. Among them are drought, unemployment and persecution (Lee, 2012).

Whereas the pull factors in the advanced nations such as infrastructure development, respect for human rights, and effective communication systems also compel migrants from the periphery to the core (Lee, 2012). Infrastructural development could not have forced the migrants to migrate to the core if the resources were to be distributed equally. Meanwhile, the underdevelopment of the periphery nations forced North-South migration, which made investors migrate to the developing nations for business purposes. If multinational companies were to be established in the periphery nations earlier, the North-South migration could have been curtailed.

The paper's findings continue that highly skilled labourers in developing countries are forced to migrate to the advanced nations to 'fit' into the economy because their skills are underutilised. The probability of not adding value to themselves in the periphery nations is possible (OECD, 2022). In another development, the

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